

RELIABILITY ANALYSIS AND FAILURE FORECAST OF CRITICAL COMPONENTS UNDER WARRANTY

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Abstract *Companies need to produce durable, safe, and quality products and adopt the best strategies to deal with the occurrence of failures when needed. This not only reduces the risk of failure but also enhances customer confidence. The present study was developed in the cargo handling and lifting industry in a way to identify critical components installed in assets based on data from failure records, and based on the results achieved, develop a reliability analysis on such critical components, allowing to describe their behavior on operating time. The reliability analysis was developed based on statistical theory, using numerical computation through specialized software. It was possible to describe the reliability, the probability of failure, the failure rate, and other characteristics that allow us to predict these probabilities for a specific operating time. Furthermore, a forecast of warranty returns was prepared through the analysis of sales vs returns, which provided an important tool to predict the failures during the warranty period, and thus plan interventions and the need for spare parts, optimizing the entire management of interventions to be carried out in the future. It is also shown that the use of computational tools in this field enhances faster and more visible results.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The topic of reliability in the cargo handling and lifting industry plays a crucial role in operational efficiency, safety, and customer satisfaction. Failures in load handling and lifting equipment pose a significant challenge. Unscheduled downtimes resulting from these failures compromise operator safety and disrupt operations. Identifying and mitigating these failures early is essential to maintaining productivity and workplace safety.

The costs associated with equipment failures are substantial and multifaceted. They include repair and replacement expenses, production losses, and possible contractual penalties for delivery delays. Additionally, indirect costs, such as loss of customer trust and damage to the company's reputation, must not be overlooked.

Frequent or unexpected failures can lead to a shortage of replacement parts, extending equipment downtime and increasing customer dissatisfaction, which can lead to contract losses, complaints, and reputational damage to the company. Unreliable equipment results in delays and disruptions that directly impact customers. Therefore, efficient spare parts inventory management and accurate maintenance forecasting are essential.

Predicting warranty returns is crucial for risk management and cost control. Analysing historical maintenance data can help to identify patterns and anticipate potential failures. This knowledge allows companies to plan with anticipation, reduce downtime, and minimize costs associated with warranty returns.

Advanced predictive maintenance techniques, the use of real-time monitoring systems, and data analysis are effective strategies to enhance reliability. Additionally, continuous operator training and the implementation of best maintenance practices can significantly contribute to reducing failures and improving equipment performance.

This study addresses issues related to equipment failures, inherent costs, warranty return forecasts, and the implications of a potential shortage of spare parts, ultimately highlighting the strategic importance of reliability for the competitiveness and sustainability of operations.

The main objectives of this study are to identify critical warranty components in a load handling and lifting company and to analyse their reliability, thereby promoting the organization's continuous improvement. This part of the study was achieved by using computational means, enhancing the results in a shorter time, and improving the visualization of distinct features.

The paper is structured into five sections. The first section makes an introduction to the theme, and the second section refers to the selection of critical items on assets, allowing to conduct further deep failure analysis. The third section deals with reliability theory and its importance, the fourth section presents a case study where a specific computational tool was used, and the fifth section discusses the results and presents some conclusions and future work.

2. SELECTION OF CRITICAL ITEMS

The selection of critical items can be performed using several tools and methods. In the present study it was done using the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) methodology. The AHP methodology was developed in the 1970s by Thomas L. Saaty at the Wharton Business School. It can be described as a multicriteria decision-making approach in which several factors are organized into a hierarchical structure [1].

2.1. Description of AHP methodology

According to Saaty [2], AHP is a methodology that uses pairwise comparisons, based on expert opinions, to derive priority scales.

In addition to simplifying the decision-making process by allowing direct comparisons between options, this method provides a greater understanding of the relationships between different alternatives in terms of compatibility [3].

According to Taherdoost [4], AHP is a valuable tool and one of the most comprehensive systems for decision-making in complex situations that require the consideration of multiple criteria, incorporating both quantitative and qualitative factors.

The AHP application process begins when a complex problem is broken down into more manageable parts, helping to structure the issue in a logical and organized manner, facilitating the independent analysis and comparison of each component.

The objective represents the desired outcome or guiding purpose of the decision-making process. The criteria are specific factors that serve as the basis for evaluating and analysing different alternatives. The alternatives refer to the various choices available for assessment about the criteria [5].

Once the logical hierarchy is designed, decision-makers can systematically evaluate the alternatives. This is done through pairwise comparisons for each previously established criterion. During these comparisons, decision-makers can use specific data related to the alternatives or make subjective judgments. This flexibility allows for the incorporation of both objective and subjective information into the decision-making process [6].

According to Saaty [2], Vargas [6], and Wollmann et al. [7], the process consists of five main phases:

1. Problem definition;
2. Structuring the decision hierarchy;
3. Construction of pairwise comparison matrices;
4. Determination of the relative weight of each element in the hierarchical structure;
5. Data consistency verification.

2.2. Use of the Analytic Hierarchy Process

Any situation that requires structuring, measurement, and involving multiple criteria is a good candidate for the use of the Analytic Hierarchy Process. Broad areas where AHP has been successful include: Choice, Prioritization/Evaluation, Resource Allocation, Quality Management, Public Policy, Healthcare, or Strategic Planning. This methodology is valuable in these contexts due to its ability to handle multiple criteria, facilitating strategic and complex decision-making [8].

One of the most comprehensive studies on AHP was conducted by Emrouznejad and Marra [9]. In this study, 8441 articles were analysed from the Web of Science database, covering an extensive period from 1979 to 2017. The study divided the evolution of AHP into three distinct periods. In the first period (1979-1990), the focus was on building the theoretical foundations of AHP; the second period (1991-2001) saw an increase in practical applications in fields such as computer science, mathematics, business, and management; and finally, the third period

(2002-2017) was characterized by the expansion of AHP into areas such as the fuzzy approach. A more recent study performed by Madzik and Falát [10] analysed 34530 documents related to AHP, published between 1980 and 2021, and obtained from the Scopus database. The authors of this study report that the remarkable growth of publications on this method is due to the ease of application, logic, and flexibility of the process. Decision-making is present in virtually all areas of research and has been applied in sectors such as engineering, computer science, business and management, mathematics, and social sciences.

3. RELIABILITY

3.1. Introduction

Reliability is one of the quality characteristics demanded by consumers from product manufacturers or service providers. Unfortunately, when asked about the meaning of reliability, consumers' answers tend to be unclear. Some may mention that the product must always function correctly, without failures, or that it should perform its function adequately when needed. Others, however, may have difficulty explaining the exact meaning of reliability to them [11].

From a technical point of view, reliability is a characteristic of an item, expressed by the probability that the item will perform its function under specific conditions over a determined period. Generally, this probability is denoted as $R(t)$. Qualitatively, reliability can be defined as the ability of the item to remain functional. From a quantitative perspective, reliability specifies the probability that no operational interruptions will occur during a predetermined time interval. This formal definition highlights that reliability does not prevent redundant parts from failing. However, even when failures occur, reliability considers the capacity for repair without operational interruption at the item or system level. The concept of reliability, therefore, applies to both non-repairable and repairable items [12].

Formally, reliability is viewed as both an engineering and probabilistic concept. Both of these perspectives form the fundamental basis for reliability studies. The engineering notion of reliability deals with design and analysis activities that extend the life of an item by controlling its potential failure modes. Examples include designing more robust and durable components, protecting against adverse environmental conditions, minimizing loads and stresses applied to an item during its use, and implementing a preventive maintenance program to reduce the occurrence of failures [13].

In summary, reliability refers to the ability of a product or service to perform its function over time, being a combination of performance characteristics, durability, and maintainability [11]. Reliability is defined by the EN 13306 standard [14] as the *“ability of an item to perform a required function under given conditions, over a given period of time.”*

3.2. Statistical distributions

A reliability analysis uses statistical distributions where times to failure are fitted. The most widely used is the Weibull distribution due to its flexibility and adequacy to most of the

studies presented in industrial cases.

Other studies use other statistical distributions as the Normal distribution, the Exponential distribution, or the Lognormal distribution.

Because of the massive use of Weibull distribution and its application in the case study presented in section 4, it will be described in more detail, addressing its fundamental characteristics and distinctive properties.

3.3. Weibull distribution

The Weibull Distribution is a continuous probability distribution named in honour of Waloddi Weibull, who described it in detail in 1951. Since then, the Weibull distribution has become one of the most referenced lifetime distributions in reliability engineering. The Weibull Distribution is capable of accurately describing the failure times observed in various types of components and phenomena [15].

The probability density function for the Weibull Distribution in its triparametric form is given by Equation (1):

$$f(t) = \left(\frac{\beta}{\eta}\right) \cdot \left(\frac{t-\gamma}{\eta}\right)^{\beta-1} \cdot e^{-\left(\frac{t-\gamma}{\eta}\right)^{\beta}} \quad (1)$$

where:

- $f(t) \geq 0, t \geq \gamma, \beta > 0, \eta > 0, -\infty < \gamma < +\infty$
- β is the shape parameter
- η is the scale parameter (or characteristic life)
- γ is the position parameter

The parameter γ is referred to as the threshold, warranty time, or, more commonly, the initial life. From a statistical perspective, it is a location parameter. This means that changing γ while the other parameters remain constant will result in a shift of the density curve along the horizontal axis [16].

The parameter η is referred to as the characteristic life. From a statistical perspective, it is a scale parameter. It indicates the time at which there is a 63.2% probability of failure.

The third parameter, also known as the slope of the Weibull Distribution, is represented by the symbol β . From a statistical perspective, β is a shape parameter. The main characteristics of the shape parameter (β) can be highlighted [17] [18]:

- If $\beta < 1$ – The failure rate decreases over time (infant mortality);
- If $\beta = 1$ – Indicates random failures, constant and independent of time (Exponential distribution);
- If $\beta > 1$ – The failure rate increases over time (wearout);
- If $3 < \beta < 4$ – The failure rate approaches a Normal distribution;
- If $\beta > 3.4$ – Indicates severe wear failures.

The main domains where the Weibull distribution has been commonly applied are [17]:

- Warranty analysis
- Maintenance and renewal
- Modeling material strength

- Modeling wear
- Modeling electronic failures
- Modeling corrosion

If the failure can occur at any moment, it is assumed that the location parameter is equal to zero, and the Weibull distribution is represented in its biparametric form, with the probability density function represented by Equation (2):

$$f(t) = \left(\frac{\beta}{\eta}\right) \cdot \left(\frac{t}{\eta}\right)^{\beta-1} \cdot e^{-\left(\frac{t}{\eta}\right)^\beta} \quad (2)$$

When the failures are random in time, it means that the shape parameter is equal to one, the Weibull distribution is resumed to its monoparametric form, as Equation (3):

$$f(t) = \left(\frac{1}{\eta}\right) \cdot e^{-\left(\frac{t}{\eta}\right)} \quad (3)$$

The main methods for estimating the parameters of the chosen distribution are the Least Squares Regression (Rank Regression) and the Maximum Likelihood Method (MLE).

Reliability can be determined by Equation (4), when dealing with the triparametric representation:

$$R(t) = e^{-\left(\frac{t-\gamma}{\eta}\right)^\beta} \quad (4)$$

The probability of failure can be easily determined because it is the complementary value of reliability, obtained by Equation (5):

$$F(t) = 1 - R(t) \quad (5)$$

The above theory supports computational applications in the field of reliability analysis, complemented with a more exhaustive theory about failure rate determination, conditional reliability, confidence intervals, and more.

4. CASE STUDY

The present case study deals with the reliability analysis and failure forecast of components installed in equipment in the cargo handling and lifting industry.

4.1. Selection

According to the AHP methodology described in Section 2, the main objective was to identify the critical component that had the most impact on the organization's warranties in recent years. The selected criteria were the number of failures, the average cost per repair, and the average repair time.

This choice of criteria allowed for a comprehensive analysis of the efficiency and effectiveness of the repair operations, considering both the quantitative aspect of the failures and the economic and time factors involved in the repair processes. In Figure 1, the hierarchical structure for this case study can be observed.

Figure 1. Hierarchical structure.

After the design of the hierarchical structure and the definition of the criteria and alternatives, the next phase involves pairwise comparisons. The comparisons of the criteria were made by company experts, and the comparison between the alternatives was based on the historical record of component failures.

Based on the set of standardized criteria, it becomes possible to derive the relative weights. The weights indicate the relative importance of each criterion concerning the others, achieving in this study the following results:

- Number of Failures = 0.544
- Average Cost per Repair = 0.243
- Average Time to Repair = 0.213

By analyzing the values resulting from the priority vector of the criteria, it is concluded that the Number of Failures is the most significant criterion, representing 54.4%. Next is the Average Time to Repair, which represents 24.3%, and last, the Average Cost per Repair, with 21.3%. These values reflect the relative relevance of each criterion in the decision-making process, highlighting the specific contribution of each in the overall evaluation.

Follows a consistency analysis of the methodology, aiming to assess the coherence and robustness of the comparisons made. This procedure is essential to verify the consistency of the comparisons performed, ensuring the strength and reliability of the results in the context of the analysis. This involves analyzing the collected data to ensure that the comparisons made during the decision-making process align with logical and coherent standards. The evaluation of data consistency was confirmed. In the present context, the matrix is considered consistent, as the Consistency Ratio (*CR*) is less than 0.10. This conclusion indicates that the comparisons made are coherent and exhibit an acceptable level of consistency, strengthening the credibility of the results obtained in the analysis.

Upon completing the consistency analysis phase for the top level of the hierarchy, the same process is now applied to the lower level. In other words, the alternatives are compared against each other, but this time for each of the specific criteria.

Based on historical data, the alternatives considered for this study are: Direction Pressure Switch, Valves and Seal Kit, Electrical Installation, Record, Load Sensor, Bolts/Ball Joints, and Brake Pressure Switch.

After the comparisons of the alternatives for each criterion and confirming the consistency

of such comparisons, the priority vector of each alternative concerning each of the criteria and the weights of the criteria was obtained.

It was then possible to calculate the overall weight of each alternative about the objective. In this sense, and according to the theory of AHP, the weights of the criteria are multiplied by the priority vectors of the alternatives, then the total value is obtained by summing the resulting products. By applying this methodology, the weights of each alternative about the objective were obtained, and they can be observed in Table 1.

Direction Pressure Switch	26.71%	1°
Bolts/Ball Joints	17.98%	2°
Vlaves and Seal Kit	17.62%	3°
Electricall Installation	14,90%	4°
Brake Pressure Switch	8.33%	5°
Load Sensor	7.95%	6°
Record	6.51%	7°

Table 1. Global weight for each alternative.

Analysing the results, it can be observed that the Direction Pressure Switch is the most important component, with 26.71%. Then, this was the item selected for a further and more accurate reliability analysis.

4.2. Reliability analysis

To begin the reliability analysis, the failures of the selected component in the last 2 years were analyzed through the ERP (Enterprise Resource Planning) system and by consulting existing work sheets.

With the identification of the failures, the serial numbers of the equipment that had failures related to the direction pressure switch were obtained. In total, 50 failures in 20 different pieces of equipment were analysed in this study.

Some components under the analysis, despite being only 2 years in service, experienced 6 failures.

Table 2 presents the times to failure (in hours) of the selected components.

The present study used a computational tool called Reliability4All. It was specially developed by a team of Reliability Engineers and was provided free of charge for conducting the analyses in this work. On the tool's home page, the Life Data Analysis module was selected.

Equipament	Failure 1	Failure 2	Failure 3	Failure 4	Failure 5	Failure 6
6740	701	1466				
7153	739					
1288	1636	3483	3821	4746		
1330	1156	2479	3357	5671		
6891	1410	2047	2835	3453	4123	4780
1833	1151	2083	3078			
1313	1204	2135	4187	5104	6722	
6767	1351	1820				
6990	2043	2849	3926	4600		
6678	1887	2938	3477			
8067	560					
6985	1582					
9824	4417	6624	7512			
2591	3927	4575				
1106	284	996				
7162	517					
6718	2109					
6886	1987	2591	3466			
3996	638					
9559	669					

Table 2. Time to failure of the component.

In this analysis, exact times to failure were chosen. Suspended times were not initially used. The distribution chosen for this analysis was the triparametric Weibull distribution, as it is, according to the literature, the most suitable for warranty studies.

The MLE (Maximum Likelihood Estimation) method was selected for parameter estimation, as it is considered one of the best methods for estimating parameters for sample sizes above 30 [19].

By calculating the parameters under the stated conditions and assuming a 90% confidence interval, the following values were obtained:

- Shape parameter (β) = 1.23
- Scale parameter (η) = 986.88 hours
- Location parameter (γ) = 277.30 hours

With these values, it is possible to determine the probability of failure or reliability for a given time, as well as the failure rate and other relevant information. Figure 2 illustrates the probability density function for the component under analysis.

Figure 2. Probability density function.

Figure 3 shows the graphical representation of the evolution of the probability of failure in time.

Figure 3. Cumulative probability of failure.

As the shape parameter is higher than 1 it means that the failure rate is increasing in time, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Failure rate.

By using the theory and analytical equations, the reliability, $R(t)$, for the direction pressure switch for any time of operation can be easily determined. For example, for 1000 hours of operation, a reliability of 0.5062 is achieved. This is confirmed by the software tool, as illustrated in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Printscreen of the reliability tool for 1000 hours

In the above figure are also visible the reliability values expected for reliability, considering the confidence interval of 90% (reliability from 0.4084 to 0.5959)

The next step refers to the inclusion of suspended times in the analysis. These times represent the time elapsed from the component's installation until the date of analysis without any recorded failure. In this sense, instead of being considered a failure, it is treated as a suspension. Thus, it was possible to determine the current hours of the equipment since the last recorded failure or since its initial installation.

Accordingly, an analysis of the failure times was performed to obtain the suspended (S) and failure (F) data to be used in this analysis. For the triparametric Weibull Distribution, similar to the previous analysis, the Maximum Likelihood Estimation (MLE) method was used for analysis. By calculating the parameters under the stated conditions, with a 90% confidence interval, 50 failures, and 12 suspensions, the following parameter values were obtained:

- Shape parameter (β) = 1.69
- Scale parameter (η) = 1435.85 hours
- Location parameter (γ) = 9.90 hours

The scale parameter (η), or the characteristic life of the component, in this case, indicates that by 1435.85 hours, approximately 63.2% of the pressure switches will have failed. With the introduction of suspended data, there was a clear improvement in the characteristic life of the component compared to the scale parameter value (986.88 hours) obtained in the first analysis. The position parameter (γ), or the initial life of the pressure switch, changed from 277.30 hours in the previous analysis to 9.90 hours with the inclusion of suspended data, meaning that the component has a possibility of failing almost immediately after being put into operation.

Similarly, it is possible to obtain graphical representation for the probability density function, probability of failure, reliability, and failure rate. Figure 6 shows the value for the reliability at 1000 hours of operation when suspended times are considered.

Figure 6. Printsreen of the reliability tool for 1000 hours (with suspensions)

As it can be seen, the result is a little better (0.5861 instead of 0.5062), confirming that the inclusion of suspended data gives a more real and positive results.

4.3. Failure forecast

To begin the failure forecast analysis, the failures of the studied component in the last 2 years were analysed. With the use of the computational tool, it was also possible to forecast returns within the warranty period. For this purpose, the Warranty Analysis - NRI (Non-Repairable Items) software module was selected, as the warranties analysed in this study involve situations where the damaged component is replaced rather than repaired.

The first step was to identify the number of units sold and the returns for each month in 2023. These data were then entered into a Nevada Chart, which can be observed in Table 3.

Period	Sales	Returns											
		feb/23	mar/23	apr/23	may/23	jun/23	jul/23	aug/23	sep/23	oct/23	nov/23	dec/23	jan/24
jan/23	21	3	3	2	1	3	2	1	1	1	1	1	1
feb/23	18		2	2	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0
mar/23	17			6	1	1	2	1	3	1	1	0	1
apr/23	7				0	0	2	0	1	0	1	0	1
may/23	19					1	0	0	1	2	1	0	1
jun/23	8						0	1	0	0	0	0	0
jul/23	16							2	1	1	0	1	2
aug/23	9								2	0	1	0	0
sep/23	5									1	2	0	0
oct/23	7										1	1	1
nov/23	16											4	1
dec/23	11												1
jan/24	14												
feb/24	7												
mar/24	10												

Table 3. Sales and returns of the component under analysis.

With the triparametric Weibull distribution, the following parameters were determined:

- Shape parameter (β) = 0.5102
- Scale parameter (η) = 9.59 months
- Location parameter (γ) = 0.99 months

This means that about 63.2% of the sold items will fail after 9.6 months.

This simulation allows us to obtain the previsional number of returns during the warranty period for the next 4 months (Table 4).

Period	Sales	feb/24	mar/24	apr/24	may/24
jan/23	21	0,05	0,04	0,04	0,04
feb/23	18	0,4	0,36	0,33	0,3
mar/23	17	0	0	0	0
apr/23	7	0,11	0,1	0,09	0,08
may/23	19	0,76	0,67	0,6	0,54
jun/23	8	0,44	0,38	0,34	0,3
jul/23	16	0,61	0,52	0,46	0,41
aug/23	9	0,45	0,37	0,32	0,28
sept/23	5	0,17	0,14	0,11	0,1
oct/23	7	0,39	0,3	0,25	0,21
nov/23	16	1,37	0,94	0,73	0,59
dec/23	11	2,49	0,94	0,64	0,5
jan/24	14	0,42	3,39	1,27	0,87
feb/24	7		0,21	1,69	0,64
mar/24	10			0,3	2,42
	Total	7,64	8,37	7,17	7,28

Table 4. Forecast for returns of the component under analysis.

During the study, it was possible to record the number of returns for the months under observation and compare it with the forecast presented in Table 6. By comparing the forecasted numbers with the actual figures, the following variations were observed:

- **February 2024:** The simulation predicted 7.64 warranty returns, while the actual number was 8, resulting in a percentage deviation of 4.48%.
- **March 2024:** The simulation predicted 8.37 warranty returns, while the actual number was 9, with a percentage deviation of 7.02%.
- **April 2024:** The simulation predicted 7.17 warranty returns, while the actual number was 7, resulting in a percentage deviation of -2.49%.
- **May 2024:** The simulation predicted 7.28 warranty returns, while the actual number was 8, with a percentage deviation of 9%.

These results indicate that the simulation forecasts are quite close to the actual values, with minor discrepancies that can be attributed to unidentified equipment or inherent forecasting variabilities. Nonetheless, it is possible to affirm that this warranty forecasting model can continue to be used for a more efficient management of returns during the warranty period.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

This work aimed to conduct a detailed reliability analysis and warranty return forecasting using robust statistical and analytical methods. The AHP methodology was essential for identifying the critical component among all evaluated items, allowing the hierarchical ranking of components based on their importance, ensuring that the study focused on the most relevant parts for the company's specific needs. This approach facilitated prioritization

and provided a solid foundation for the subsequent reliability analysis steps.

The reliability analysis was developed using statistical models to determine the most suitable distribution for the failure data (Weibull distribution). After that, a new analysis was also conducted to include suspended data. With the introduction of suspended data into the Weibull distribution, a significant improvement was observed in the component's characteristic life compared to the value obtained in the first analysis. In summary, incorporating suspended data significantly improves the reliability of the models.

To complete the study, a warranty return forecast was conducted based on monthly sales in 2023 and the subsequent recorded warranty returns. The model's accuracy was validated by comparing forecasted values with actual results, where the maximum percentage deviation was 9%. This result indicates that the developed model is reliable and can be used for future warranty return predictions.

This study demonstrated the effectiveness of combining different analytical and statistical methods for reliability analysis and warranty return forecasting and the advantage of using computational tools in this type of analysis. Furthermore, the practical application of this study's findings can lead to significant improvements in warranty management and the reliability of analysed systems within the company's structure.

For future work, it is recommended to explore the integration of machine learning techniques and big data analytics to enhance prediction accuracy and the effectiveness of reliability analysis.

Additionally, it is suggested that all components exhibiting recurring failures undergo a reliability analysis to determine their useful life expectancy and ensure an adequate stock supply based on the number of existing equipment units. Implementing such measures is essential to ensure operational continuity and optimize resource management. Lastly, by contributing to predictive maintenance, these measures promote a culture of continuous improvement within the organization. In this way, the company increases the reliability and lifespan of its equipment, optimises resources, and enhances customer satisfaction.

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